

PREPARATION OF FUTURE TECHNOLOGY TEACHERS FOR CREATIVE ACTIVITY

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Abstract. *In this article, the content of preparing future technology teachers for creative activities, types of creative activities and stages of development of creative activities, issues of improving modeling and design skills are described scientifically.*

Keywords: *creativity, creative activity, activity, flexibility of thinking, criticality, development, design.*

INTRODUCTION

The importance of the intellectual potential of people in scientific and technical development, managing the socio-economic development of the country and determining its future is shown on the world scale. At the same time, the current state of the development of science around the world, especially in a society where education is widely introduced to young people, the rapid updating of knowledge in various fields of science, in addition to the rapid acquisition of them, set the task of regularly and independently seeking knowledge for students. In the modern conditions of education development, the task of forming the skills of future teachers to act quickly in new, non-standard situations, to analyze existing sources of information and to act creatively in changing the surrounding space is urgent. This requires a high level of creativity.

"Creative activity" is very important and relevant at the moment, and as a result of the rapid multifaceted development of science, the constant change and complexity of technical means of production, the future specialists who are studying in the field of technological education will be creative in their future pedagogical activities, including the updating of changes at the state level, in this case, it consists in finding the characteristics of creativity, inventiveness, and striving for innovation.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The creativity of the teacher's personality is improved by his attitude to his work, stability, activity, abilities, skills, and characterized achievement of results.

Improving the professional competence of future specialists in ensuring the effectiveness of the modern educational process is now extremely important. In this field, scientists are carrying out important and extensive work. In particular, in the works of Sh.S. Sharipov, the concepts of creativity were clarified and the periods of its implementation were developed. At the same time, the criteria for selecting the content of the multi-level programmed educational process of forming inventive creativity in students have been developed. [1].

In the thesis of O.A. Koysynov, the technologies of developing the professional and pedagogical creativity of future vocational education teachers based on a competent approach are highlighted [2,10].

Creativity is a process of active human activity, which implies the creation of a unique result, which has a material or spiritual expression, regardless of the initial conditions. In this process, creativity has clear differences from production. The result obtained in the process of creative activity is unique, and the author can achieve it because he has been able to include his

personal ideas and understanding of life in his work. Therefore, the products of creative activity have a special value. The psychological aspect plays an important role in creativity. To create any creative product, a person must have certain abilities, knowledge and skills.

A.I. Savenkov said that "not every activity is creativity, but any creativity is an activity." The activity itself appears as a component of the creative process [3].

In the pedagogical encyclopedia, creativity is interpreted as the highest form of activity and independence in human activity, which is manifested in the need to change, improve, create new and unique things. Many pedagogues and psychologists define creativity in scientific works in the context of the concept of "creative activity" (V.I.Andreev, T.I.Shamova) [4,5].

D. B. Bogoyavlenskaya defines creative activity as an intellectual activity that combines mental abilities and motivational personal factors [6].

V.A.Petrovsky and I.S.Yakimanskaya consider creative activity to be a personal property, a feature that determines the direction of self-improvement, a necessary condition for a person's self-realization. G. I. Shchukina explains creative activity as a personal formation that expresses the state of the student and his attitude to the activity, including: attention, active participation in the process, quick response [7,8].

According to A.I.Karmanchikov, creative activity is a set of personal characteristics that allow to ensure the interaction of internal and external factors in the process of creating new knowledge, and creative activity is the initiative of a person, the potential of effective activity. [9].

RESULTS

Creativity is a conscious, purposeful process in which a person realizes self-awareness and personal development. Consequently, a person's creative activity largely depends on his activity, mental abilities, intuition, imagination and other personal qualities. Taking this into account, the stages of the preparation of future technology teachers for creative activities and their intellectual preparation are carried out in the following sequence: **(Figure 1)**

Figure 1. The process of intellectual preparation of the student in the preparation of future technology teachers for creative activity.

From our point of view, creativity is the process of creating something new, as a result of which changes occur in the person who performs this type of activity. The subject's creative activity, its unique result is determined by his needs, knowledge, skills and qualifications..

The preparation of future technology teachers for creative activities is carried out by integrating three main factors:

- modularity, which ensures the appropriateness of the organization of educational content based on the concept of didactically adapted knowledge, structured in accordance with the basic competencies that reflect the specific characteristics of the professional activity of a specialist in a particular field;

- organization of education according to activity, which determines the choice of forms of education corresponding to the purpose of education;

- technologyzation of education - aimed at ensuring the full development of a person by organizing a continuous process of education and development.

Experiences of creative activities, which are part of the educational content, are created by applying the previously acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of students in new unexpected situations [11]. For this reason, it is necessary for the teacher in the educational process not to provide knowledge in the form of ready-made information, but as a result of creating problematic situations, to create an opportunity for students to apply the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in previous topics in new unexpected situations, to prepare the ground for the development of independent and creative thinking skills in them. (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Stages of creative thinking in future technology teachers.

The level of creative development of a person is manifested in the reflection of "I can", "I want" and in understanding the reason for one's development, in the skill of setting goals and tasks

for self-change and self-improvement. Psychological innovations of this level are provided by adequate self-reflection, the ability to analyze one's actions, foreseeing their consequences.

A high level of creative development allows you to work effectively without other people noticing.

This level shows emotional stability in planning one's activities, implementing one's skills, predicting one's work (prospecting), defending one's point of view, being independent in practice.

DISCUSSION

A teacher's pedagogic skills cannot be created and improved without intelligence, thinking, creative activity. In any type of teacher's creative activity, both his mental and physical work are objectively involved at the same time. Creative activity is the basis of a teacher's life. In the mind of a teacher, any thought, any vision and understanding is not born and developed by itself. Rather, all of them are connected to some extent with creative ideas.

A form of human or collective activity is a way of stimulating, creating something that did not exist before, but qualitatively new. The original product of creative activity is the formation of a non-standard hypothesis, the interdependence of the elements of a non-traditional problem situation, the involvement of directly related elements, the establishment of new types of interdependence between them. As prerequisites for this - **flexibility of thinking** (the ability to change the methods of solving), **criticality** (the ability to abandon ineffective strategies), the ability **to combine** and **harmonize concepts**, the integrity of perception. The creation of creative abilities is unique, and creativity encompasses everything from great and brilliant talent to subtle and perfect. But the essence of the creative process is the same for everyone, it is manifested in the unique content of creativity, the scale of achievements and their importance in society.

CONCLUSION

The preparation of future technology teachers for creative activities is related to the organization and management of educational processes in higher educational institutions, independent learning, research, learning the methods and ways of consciously perfect learning of each subject, improving the characteristics of developing one's own knowledge.

Creative activity greatly helps in forming a high culture of students, mastering the tools and methods of education, rational spending and planning of their time, collecting and mastering information necessary for successful education and professional formation. Creative activity develops students' organization, discipline, initiative, will, thinking and analytical skills, teaches them to think independently, and allows them to create their own independent work style.

In the implementation of the goals and tasks of preparing future teachers of technology for creative activities, each student should acquire and observe the taught subjects in depth, be able to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, use additional literature in this field, be able to analyze different views and approaches to the topic, and the issues expressed in the topic, to express one's attitude boldly and competently, to properly organize the experiences of writing abstracts, course work, graduation qualification work, master's dissertations, to serve to spend free time productively, to work creatively with scientific and special literature on the relevant subject and other sources.

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